

COMPARING OF GENERAL HEALTH, LIFE EXPECTANCY AND HAPPINESS OF MOTHERS OF MENTALLY RETARDED CHILDREN WITH MOTHERS OF NORMAL CHILDREN

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Abstract:

Because the pressure of having a disabled child, parents are forced to withdraw from normal social contacts. Parents, especially mothers are withdrawn due to the increase in social exclusion and isolation; parents tend to permanent focus too much on children's activities. The increased attention to children's disabilities brings psychological disturbances and reduces the life expectancy of mothers. This study compared general health, happiness and hope to the lives of mothers of normal children with mothers of mental retard children. The present study was using causal-comparative methods. Participants in the study mothers of mental retard and normal school students in Sari province were selected. 200 mothers (100 mental retard students mothers and 100 of normal students' mothers) were selected through cloning method. Miller hopes questionnaire, questionnaire with 28 questions GHO, Oxford Happiness Questionnaire were used as research tools for statistical analysis of data, descriptive statistics (such as frequency tables, charts, etc.) and inferential statistics, independent t-test to compare two groups were used. The results showed that between hope, health and happiness of mothers of mental retard and normal students the difference was significant. The results showed that students' disabilities have negative effects on their mothers' public health, hope, and happiness.

Key word: hope, happiness, general health, mental retard

1. Introduction

If mental health problems are not recognized and left untreated, they will escalate over time, therefore, they will leave a direct impact on family atmosphere and disabled child. Based on previous studies on parents' psychological disorders, child attachment and its

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behavioral, social, emotional cognitive change and he / she will be at risk of developing the psychological disorders (Kondal, 2007). In one hand, parents with disabled child, in terms of performance and compatibility have weakness and failures rather than parents with normal child. Thus, in order to represent the consulting, educational services and psychological support is important (Ahmadi, 2011). This research paves the way for recognizing and following psychological disorders. So, with holding educational sessions and promoting the awareness of parents with disabled child and providing them with controlling stress and dealing with existing problems because of disabled child and publishing the scientific texts with simple and understandable expression helps to parents informing. On the other hand, with respect to a little researches which are done in this field, and disagreements about difference in exist of psychological disorders among disabled child parents and normal child parents, this research helps the exceptional education department officials and welfare department in the amount of prevalence and the status of mental health and personality characteristics of mentally retarded children's families so that related officials with consultation and guidance to disabled children's parents provide self-esteem and peace of mind for them. Correct servicing and identifying family problems can help to reducing the emotional distress, trying to prevention and their better education and social organization.

2. Statement of the problem

Parents, especially mother not only shows emotional reaction to their disabled child but also about people's reaction or attitude toward mentally retarded persons in the society are important for them. These pressures often force them to avoid their ordinary social communications. Parents, especially mothers, become dissociable unintentionally then, because of increasing the social rejection and isolation, they tend to permanent and extra focus on child activities. This increasing of attention and focusing on child disabilities will lead to more mental and personality disorders (Afrooz, 2006). Vin Reaper (2008) in a study on 55 families who had mentally retarded children found that these children's parents in all field rather than control group experience more stressors. The result of Reyhani research (1995) is similar to Reaper. Noori (1997) in a study about the stress found that there is a meaningful difference between the experienced stresses by the mothers of slight mentally retarded, semi-hearing, semi-slighted children rather than normal children's mothers (Komijani, 2012). In a new research by Fiqun, Safari, Faramarzi, Jamali (2013), 90 mothers of children with special needs (30 syndromes down, 30 autism and 30 cerebral palsy) and 30 mothers of normal children in Esfahan elementary schools were selected randomly (Afrooz, 2006). The results have shown that in terms of social anxiety, there is a meaningful difference between the mothers with special needs children and the mothers of normal children and the mothers of children with autism more than the mothers of mentally retarded and cerebral palsy children suffer from social anxiety.

Many factors are involved in creating the mental pressure on parents and intensifying it. Related problems with child protection have a close relationship with the amount of parents' mental pressure. Mentally retarded child's parents must accept his/her limitations and behave according to his/her limit opacity. They should refuse expectations which are more than the child's capacity. The status of those children with intelligence quotient (IQ) 50-80 is largely depends on their emotional health. If such a child has self-esteem and his/her parents support him and feels that they don't have extra expectations, will be able to deal with environment problems. Accepting the reality that mentally retarded children are limited in terms of intellectual and social progress is the key of mental health (Shamloo, 2008). In fact, disappointment lead to weakening the skill of solving problem in the person and cause to person constantly evaluates his/her experiences negatively or incorrectly and consider worrying consequences for his/her problems Shams et al., 2007. The aim of this research is the necessity of identifying the accurate amount of mental pressure to the parents of such children and evaluating their mental problems. On the other hand, with their early detection, we can educate necessary strategies for coping with mental pressure to the parents. Educating to family and early detection can reduce the sadness, fatigue, disappointment and feeling guilty of such parents. Another goal of this research is to provide a model of communication between general health with life expectancy, happiness and anxiety and depression in mothers of mental retard children. I will find ways of coping and preventing the mental problems of mothers of mental retard students. In this context, I will present a model for consultants and school administrators with special needs. Is there any significant difference between public health, life expectancy and welfare mothers of mental retard children with mothers of normal children?

3. Methodology

The present research was done during 2015-2016 in the schools under the exceptional education supervision. In terms of situation, its implementation is a field study and according to quantity and data collection method, it is a quantitative research. This research in terms of goal is applicable in exceptional education. This research has paid attention on studying the public health, life expectancy and happiness of mentally retarded children's mothers and comparing with normal children; also, the sample size in exceptional children's mothers was selected equal with statistical population. Then, the sample size of normal children's mothers was selected by matching method. The mothers of mentally retarded children in the exceptional schools of zone 1 Sari were selected that their number is 100. The sample size in the group of mentally retarded children's mothers was equal with statistical population and in the normal children's mothers was selected by matching method.

4. Findings of Study

The purpose of this study is to compare the general health and happiness of life expectancies of mothers of normal students with mothers of mental retard students in Sari city. In the present chapter, the results of research data are descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation), and inferential statistics of independent t-test and regression were used. A sample of 100 mothers of mental retard students in exceptional schools in Sari City was selected and in the normal sample, 100 mothers of normal students were selected through matching method.

Hypothesis 1: There is difference between the public health of mental retard children's mothers and normal children's mothers.

Table 4.1

Std. Deviation	Variance	Median	Mean	Group
6.52172	42.533	17.0000	16.9500	Normal children's mothers
9.57334	91.649	18.0000	20.2600	Mental retard children's mothers

With respect to the table 1, in comparison with the public health of normal children's mothers and mentally retarded children's mothers, the public health average score of mentally retarded children's mothers was 20.26 and public health of normal children's mothers was 16.95. The results have shown that the public health of normal mothers has attained lower score then has higher health. On the basis of Skewness 1 is between 2 to -2 that shows that the scores are normal.

Table 4.2

Independent Samples Test											
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances				t-test for Equality of Means					
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
										Lower	Upper
Emtyaz	Equal variances assumed	7.514	.007	-2.857	198	.005	-3.31000	1.15837	-5.59432	-1.02568	
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.857	174.605	.005	-3.31000	1.15837	-5.59621	-1.02379	

In order to analyze the above hypothesis, independent statistical t-test was used and the results have shown that the difference of public health of normal students' mothers and mentally retarded students' mothers became meaningful.

Hypothesis 2: There is difference between the life expectancy of mental retard children's mothers and normal children's mothers.

Table 4.3

Std. Deviation	Variance	Median	Mean	Group
21.74141	472.689	184.0000	183.0900	Normal children's mothers
25.51901	651.220	175.0000	170.7500	Mental retard children's mothers

The average score of table 4.3 has shown that in comparison to the hope of normal students' mothers and mentally retarded students, the hope of mentally retarded students' mothers was 170.75 and for normal students' mothers was 183.09. The results have shown that normal students' mothers have higher hope.

Table 4.4

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means							
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
										Lower	Upper
Emtyaz	Equal variances assumed	3.812	.052	3.681	198	.000	12.34000	3.35247	5.72886	18.95114	
	Equal variances not assumed			3.681	193.127	.000	12.34000	3.35247	5.72784	18.95216	

In table 4.4, for studying the above hypothesis, independent statistical t-test was used and the results have shown that life expectancy of normal students' mothers in comparison to autistic students' mothers had a meaningful difference. $P= 0.000$

Hypothesis 3: There is difference between the happiness of mental retard children's mothers and normal children's mothers.

With respect to table 4.5, in comparison to the happiness of normal students' mothers and mentally retarded students' mothers, the average score for the happiness of mentally retarded mothers was 32.21 and for normal students' mothers were 39.03. The results have shown that normal mothers had higher score in happiness then had more happiness.

Table 4.5

Std. Deviation	Variance	Median	Mean	Group
15.41707	237.686	40.0000	39.0300	Normal children's mothers
14.52291	210.915	32.5000	32.2100	Mental retard children's mothers

Table 4.6

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
				F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
		Lower	Upper							
Score	Equal variances assumed	.004	.949	3.220	198	.001	6.82000	2.11802	2.64323	10.99677
	Equal variances not assumed			3.220	197.297	.001	6.82000	2.11802	2.64314	10.99686

For analyzing the above hypothesis, independent statistical t-test was used and the results have shown that happiness of normal students' mothers in comparison to mentally retarded students' mothers had a meaningful difference. $P= 0.001$

5. Discussion

The result of the first hypothesis has shown that there is a meaningful difference between the public health of the mothers with mentally retarded students and mothers with normal students and their results is the same with Moosavi Khatat researches (2011). In the new research of Fiqan, Safari, Farmarzi, Jamali (2013) 90 mothers of children with special needs (30 syndrome down, 30 autism, 30 cerebral palsy) and 30 mothers of normal children of elementary school of Isfahan county are selected randomly. The results have shown that there is a meaningful difference in terms of social anxiety among mothers of children with special needs and mothers of normal children. That shows that is the same with this research. Rerdon (2007) during a research in Australia has shown that mothers of mentally retarded children have less time for occupation and paying to enjoyable activities and entertainment. Also, this research has shown that, mother's time for personal cares will be reduced. Therefore, mothers because of less time for them will be more vulnerable (Komijani, 2012). This research is favorable with Arnoved et al, (2008) which have shown that mothers of disabled children have some problems about mental health, life expectancy, stress, anxiety, disappointment, depression and unhappiness with their children. Khazaei

(2015) in a research on 121 mothers with normal and mentally retarded children has shown that mothers of exceptional children have less mental health rather than mothers of normal children. But the findings of Koidmir and Toson research (2009) in which is paid to studding the effect of having an autistic child on mothers life to semi – structure interviews has shown that psychiatric experiences of these mothers is such as another mothers who have experience's with other disorders. Koid Mir and Toson research (2009) has shown that, it is in consistent with present study.

The result of the hypothesis 2, the life expectancy of mothers with mentally retarded student and mothers of normal students has a meaningful difference and the result of this research with shams et.al research (2005) and with Pisula study (2005) determines that as soon as parents awareness from their children's disability, all of their dreams turns will turn to disappointment and their problems will begin, Is the same. This research is consistent with Afshari (2004) and Tajeri research (2008). The result of the hypothesis 3, happiness of those mothers with mentally retarded children with happiness of mothers with normal children with happiness of mothers with normal children had meaningful difference and present study is consistent with Mohammadi Zade that has shown that there is a meaningful difference between the happiness of mothers with mentally retarded students and mothers of normal students. Because of so many problems of mentally retarded children, their family, especially their mothers suffer from so many tensions and mental pressures, and then have less happiness (Mohammadizade, 2005). Other performed studies have shown that, the negative effects of having a mentally retarded or disable children can result in tension – pressure among family members especially for mothers then lead to her less happiness Tajeri (2008). Therefore, related research is the same with this research in Ride and Brant research, mental health and happiness of mothers with exceptional children is less than mothers with normal children. (Narimani, et al, 2007).

In Khooshbi et al, the amount of mental pressure in the mothers of exceptional children is more than the mothers belonging normal group. (Afshar, 2004). These people who have mental and behavioral pressure because of having a mentally retorted child, less the ability for coping it, then physically, mentally and morally take in to trouble (Malek Pour, 2000). Mothers of disabled children can be vulnerable due to their children's problems and feel anxious with negative feelings about their abilities for attaining their goals and lessing their hopes. (Ogstrol, Mctach, 2011). Using contrastive strategy which is excitement – oriented when coping with complexity in the parents of exceptional children is more than normal children (Rajabi Damavadi et al, 2009).

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